

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND MIX BEHAVIOUR OF RUBBERISED CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

Waste recycled rubber tyres are a significant worldwide problem with hundreds of millions more being produced annually. To alleviate this issue, high volume applications must be found which can best utilise recycled rubber. The current project involves modification of concrete properties through rubber aggregate substitution by volume, producing rubberised concrete. The purpose of the paper is to investigate the behaviour of rubberised concrete and the effect different treatments of rubber may have on it. A control mix of C40 was designed and tested. A series of subsequent mixes containing either coarse rubber aggregates at various percentage replacements by volume of natural aggregate were produced. A series of engineering tests were conducted in order to investigate the effect rubber aggregate replacement had on concrete. To further increase the benefits and minimise detriments to the concrete mix due to the addition of rubber aggregates, plain rubber was either coated with cement paste or washed with water. It was observed that the reduction in strength of the concrete mix very much depended of the grading of the rubber aggregate, the type of surface treatment the rubber aggregate was subjected to, as well as the percentage replacement of the natural aggregate. It was also observed that rubber naturally repels water and has a tendency to entrap air in its jagged surface. As a result, some difficulties when manufacturing rubberised concrete can arise. These issues are explained in the paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the UK alone over 55 million waste tyres are produced each year according to the environmental agency. In 2010, just over 30 percent of waste tyres were turned into crumb, 18 percent were used in energy recovery, nearly 20 percent were re-used (in the UK or abroad), 16 percent were specifically used in landfill engineering and 11 percent were re-treaded [1]. The European landfill directive means that this type of waste disposal would be illegal in Europe. Since 2006, EU rules have banned the disposal of tyres in landfill sites, leaving about 480,000 tonnes of recyclable shredded rubber each year [2]. Reutilisation of waste materials such as automobile tyres has been of significant interest to researchers for many years. Although more recent findings have presented potential uses for rubber, large volume application in the engineering industry is mostly unheard of. With each year passing even greater quantities of waste rubber accumulate posing environmental and health risks that will

prove all the more difficult to manage unless a readily accepted industrial scale utilisation of the resource is found.

Rubber particles have been used in the past [3], [4] to increase concrete properties such as impact resistance, energy absorption and toughness whilst reducing the unit weight of the concrete. Properties such as, tensile, flexural and compressive strengths are all known to suffer as a result of increased rubber content [4],[5], [6]. Workability is also thought to reduce with increased rubber content [7], [8], though not all research attests to this [9].

2 EXPERIMENTATION

The aim of this paper is to highlight certain characteristics of rubber particles and their potential effect on a concrete matrix in both its fresh and hardened state. Compressive strength tests results are also discussed and analysed for coarse rubber aggregates of various surface treatment. Plain crumb rubber samples were also produced for comparison with previous research.

2.1 Mix design and testing materials

A control mix with a target compressive strength of 40MPa, designated ‘Mix Design A’ (see table 1) was used in order to be compatible with future mixes involving the use of different rubber aggregate sizes. Sand <4mm diameter and Coarse aggregate graded 20-12mm was used, along with rubber aggregate ranging from 20-12mm (although certain rubber aggregates are considered elongated in nature). Super Plasticiser ADVA 650 was used at a ratio of 8.57ml/Kg of cement consistently throughout all samples.

Mix Design	Cement	Fine Aggregate	Coarse Aggregate	Water	Super plasticiser	Volume
A	375kg	710kg	1110kg	180kg	3213.75ml	1m ³

Table 1: Concrete Mix Design

Mix	Rubber Type	Sample Coding	Rubber Content (%)
<i>AP</i>	Plain Coarse	AP5	5
		AP10	10
		AP15	15
		AP20	20
<i>AC</i>	Cement Paste Coated Coarse	AC5	5
		AC10	10
		AC15	15
		AC20	20
<i>AW</i>	Water Washed Coarse	AC5	5
		AC10	10
		AC15	15
		AC20	20
<i>APF</i>	Plain Fine	APF5	5
		APF10	10
		APF15	15
		APF20	20

Table 2: Summary of contents for rubberised concrete

2.2 Sample preparation

Concrete cubes of size 100mm underwent compressive tests after 7, 14 and 28 days of curing. Natural coarse aggregates were replaced with Rubber aggregate as a percentage by volume due to the lower density of rubber particles ($G_s = 1.14$). Plain rubber was used in the concrete mix as sourced. Surface treatment used also included Cement Paste coated and water washed coarse rubber aggregates (see table 2). References and images to other sample types are included in the paper for the purpose of observation.

3 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A strength increase of approximately 10% in compressive strength was noted between controls samples tested at 28 days of curing. As a result, all subsequent mixes involving rubber had the same amount of super plasticiser added for both increased strength as well as for comparative means. Figure 1 below shows the strength development over 7, 14 and 28 day curing periods for all samples containing coarse rubber aggregate replacements (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Coarse Rubberised Concrete Compressive Strength over time

Figure 2: Compressive Strength reduction vs increased rubber content

As can be seen in figure 2, at 5% coarse aggregate replacement by volume, a slight increase in compressive strength occurred. The water washed aggregate suffered the most significant strength reduction 5% replacement by volume. The potential causes for this could be excess water left on rubber particles from the washing process. After this, Water washed rubber aggregates suffer less compressive strength reduction relative to the batch control than plain rubber, although never exceeding 4% less in comparative strength reduction. Cement paste coated rubber performed the best, with its comparative strength reduction being less than half that Plain and Water washed aggregates even at 20% aggregate replacement. Reasons for strength increase of water washed aggregates could be attributed to minor removal of surface contaminants on rubber particles that may affect the hydration process of concrete (see section 4.2). The more significant increase in strength of the cement paste coated rubber is a result of the increased compatibility in stiffness between the rubber aggregate and the concrete matrix [10].

The reduction in strength of plain fine rubber aggregate is noticeable lower than both plain and water washed coarse rubber. Reasons for the more limited strength reduction most likely pertain to the quantity of rubber present in the concrete mix being less and therefore having a more limited effect on strength reduction on the concrete mix [9]. There is 36% less fine rubber aggregates in the mix than there is coarse, meaning that any percentage replacement by volume of coarse rubber would result in a larger rubber content in the concrete mix, potentially limiting the overall strength reduction possible by a respective crumb/fine rubber aggregate replacement.

3.1 Comparison with other findings

A mix consisting of crumb rubber was compared to that of previous researchers [3]. As can be seen in figure 3, there is a very strong correlation between current and past research with regards to the compressive strength decline of concrete as the volume of crumb rubber increases. Whilst compressive strength has been known to deteriorate from any increase in rubber content [4], [6] matching Crumb rubber results as well as water washed coarse rubber, other research corresponds to slight increases in compressive strength at low percentage replacement no greater than 5% [11] of a specified measurement.

Figure 3: Coarse and Fine rubber vs Fine rubber from past research

Super plasticiser was used at a constant level relative to the cement content of the mix in order to observe the reduction in slump values as the percentage replacement of rubber aggregates increased. Furthermore, as it was detected that its presence affected the strength of the samples positively, it was concluded that varying the amount present in each batch could distort the strength data. In order to obtain consistent data, it was necessary to remove this potential variable. Despite efforts made to remove this factor, other properties inherent to the rubber particles sourced for this research presented themselves, resulting in data outliers and in some cases the need to expand the sample pool size in order to achieve a scientifically acceptable data set. There are difficulties that may arise during the manufacturing process of rubberised that, if left unchecked, have the potential to result in greater variations in compressive strength data than expected or is acceptable for a reliable conclusion to be drawn.

4 OBSERVATIONS

4.1 FRESH STATE OBSERVATIONS

4.1.1 Bleeding and segregation

Figure 4A: Segregated wet mix. 4B: Homogenous wet mix

Issues with regards to bleeding and segregation in a rubberised concrete mix are clearly evident from both this and past research (see figure 4A above). The introduction of rubber particles increases the tendency towards segregation due to its hydrophobic nature as well as its low density. Both Najim [12] and Elchalakani [13] make reference to several researchers suggesting all dry mix components should first be mixed between 1 and 5 minutes before gradually adding water as well as super plasticiser if specified. Mixing should further continue for 3 to 5 minutes or until homogenous. An alternative equally documented in past research [11],[12],[13] is that of dry mixing coarse aggregate and powder, followed by the gradual addition of fine aggregate, rubber and water with approximately 75% of the super plasticiser with the remaining 25% added later during the final 3 minutes of the mixing process. Yet another method appearing in both papers [12], [13] is that of fine and coarse natural aggregates along with half of the rubber being mixed with only a quarter of water initially. Cement/powder is then added along with a further half of the water, before gradually adding the remaining quarter whilst mixing for an additional 3-5 minutes. It is not clear in either description at what stage the other half of the remaining rubber aggregates are to be implemented in the mix design.

The mix procedure methodology undertaken in this paper closely follows the latter mix design suggestions with minor alterations derived from the former methodologies as deemed appropriate by the author. All natural aggregates and rubber were mixed together for 1-3 minutes. Half of the water was then added and mixed again for 1-3 minutes and left to be absorbed for 5-8 minutes before adding the cement. The remainder of the water (along with the super plasticiser) are the last components to be added before final mixing in order to reduce potential absorption of the super plasticiser by the dry aggregates. Segregation of the wet mix was able to be overcome by ensuring the final mixing process continued for approximately 3 to 5 minutes, although at lower percentage rubber content (< 20%), it was found that a standard mixing time of 2 minutes proved adequate to sufficiently homogenise the mix.

4.1.2 Workability

A general trend of reduction in workability was observed as the percentage of rubber increased. This is attributed to the surface texture of the rubber particles inducing increased levels of inter-particle friction between the mix constituents. An overall reduction in the unit weight of the plastic mix combined with the above are stated to be the primary reasons behind the increased slump reduction which corresponds to increased rubber aggregate content. Increased difficulty in obtaining accurate and consistent slump values in this instance was attributed to the use of super plasticiser.

4.2 HARDENED STATE OBSERVATIONS

4.2.1 Air Voids

The possibility for increased air content in rubberised concrete mixes is resultant from a number of factors. Recycled rubber may often be manufactured without consideration for engineering applications, resulting in more limited particle grading than the natural aggregate it is intended to replace in the concrete. It is possible that such limitations may decrease if further development of the tyre recycling industry is made due to an increased demand for high volume engineering applications using recycled rubber in concrete. Unequal grading between rubber replacement and the natural aggregate will therefore result in excess air pockets being generated at higher volumes of aggregate replacement. The hydrophobic nature of rubber also entraps air when the concrete is in a fresh mix state as is discussed in further detail in section 4.2.2.

Furthermore, Eldin and Senouci [8] noted that when mixed with cement the rubber aggregate tends to act as a large void and did not have a significant role in the resistance to applied external loading. In effect due to the significantly lower modulus (stiffness) of the rubber particles relative to their surrounding media (concrete matrix), rubber particles are both acting as, as well as causing an increase in air voids content cause increased stress concentration under loading conditions, hence reducing the overall strength of the concrete [10]. Combined with the hydrophobic nature of rubber as well as the hydrophilic nature of cement paste, the ability for a strong chemical bond to develop between the two is severely impeded without augmentation of the plain rubber aggregate such as surface treatment. This being the case, one can expect a consistent reduction in compressive strength when using rubberised concrete throughout all samples.

4.2.2 Intra Sample Homogeneity

When working with rubber aggregates, even if one follows a mixing procedure that enables reduced bleeding and segregation, producing a relatively homogenous mix, the homogeneity of the samples can still be affected due to the properties of rubber aggregates. As has been stated by past researchers, rubber aggregates entrap air in their jagged, rough surface texture as it repels water as well as the non-polar nature of the particle surface [12]. This therefore enables the rubber aggregates to float in a fresh concrete mix despite having a specific gravity of approximately 1.14 [14]. Although this effect is present when the concrete is in a fresh state, it is not always definitively observable until analysis of the sample in its hard state is performed.

Rubber aggregates either 'rising' to or staying at the surface is evident in figure 5 below. Whilst rubber particles are able to rise in the wet concrete mix as a result of air entrapment around the particles themselves, other factors inherent to rubber particles can often contribute to this further. For instance, due to rubber being able to absorb energy in the form of both impact and vibration, attempts to distribute the rubber evenly throughout the individual sample by means of a vibrating table can be significantly hindered depending on the level of rubber aggregates present in the mix design. When crumb rubber replaced fine aggregates by up to 70% volume, the quantity of rubber present in a cylinder sample of 150mm x 300mm was significant enough that it was able to resist an appreciable amount of vibration, resulting in a lack of homogenous distribution of rubber particles throughout the concrete matrix. Of note, the same issue can also be observed in concrete beams of dimensions 150mm x 100mm x 1500mm at a significantly lower percentage aggregate replacement by volume ($\leq 20\%$). This could indicate that the quantity of rubber present, irrespective of its relative percentage replacement of natural aggregates, is a more significant factor when concerning its ability to resist vibration and remain non-homogeneously distributed throughout the concrete matrix.

This has the potential to increase the variance between results between samples of the same batch for a number of different tests; such being the case despite a potentially identical quantity of rubber

particles being present in each sample. This can be expected to be the case for all mixes using plain rubber in concrete. The extent of the aforementioned effects may inherently vary from sample to sample based on both the sample dimensions as well as rubber aggregate percentage replacement by volume. At lower levels of aggregate replacement, unevenly distributed rubber within a sample may have limited effect if present. At levels exceeding 70% however, crack propagation could be significantly affected with excessive and uneven concentrations of rubber particles. Due to poor interfacial transition zone bonding between the rubber particles and the concrete matrix, premature failure of the sample may occur [11].

Figure 5A, B: Rubber particle distribution at 70% fine aggregate replacement by volume

Light areas of shading in figure 5 are large concentrations of cement paste within the sample. Due to the rubber particles staying at/floating to the surface, the cement paste is in turn displaced due to areas at the top of the sample having an excess volume of rubber particles present which should be partly occupied by cement in an intra-homogeneous sample. Furthermore, limited quantities of natural fine aggregate remain to mix with the cement due to the high level of crumb rubber aggregate replacement. This could result in localized strength reduction due to the cement particles having a more limited range of graded aggregates to bond with, resulting in weaker inter-particle bonds.

4.2.3 Hydrocarbon Contaminates

One possible explanation for the evident persistent variation in compressive strength of rubberised concrete is that of the natural hydration process of the concrete matrix being adversely affected due to the presence of the rubber particles. A chemical analysis using infrared surface scanning was conducted on a number of rubber samples consisting of both coarse and fine in both a washed and from unwashed state. The results displayed (figure 6) were analysed using a library index database. This indicated in some instances an 85.07% match to 'Ethyl Triacontanoate, 98%' as well as an 80.70% match to 'Tritriacontane, 98%'. Across various samples, the index match percentage value between these two chemicals were interchangeable, yet they were the most consistently predominant matches, with a number of other hydrocarbons ranging in index match from 80%-74%.

Figure 6: Infrared surface scan of coarse rubber particles

Whilst the index library search criteria may not be considered definitive evidence of specific chemicals being present, it does indicate trace levels of hydrocarbons being present on the surface of the rubber, more specifically those of the alkane family. Alkanes are commonly used in fuels such as petrol and diesel, whilst paraffin substances used in lubricants are derived from them. One could conclude that residual or imbedded hydrocarbons of such nature have been left on the sourced coarse rubber aggregates used in experimentation. The plausibility of such substances contaminating the rubber is quite high due to the life cycle of rubber tyres. Leakages on the road surface from vehicles, as well as potential contamination from lubricants used in the rubber shredding process are two such possibilities. Note that the coarse and fine rubber aggregates were sourced from different companies and the level of refinement of the material visibly varied quite significantly. As a result of this, the presence of such chemicals being detectable on the fine (or crumb) rubber was significantly less on the unwashed samples, though not entirely absent on all samples. One could conclude however that its presence would be to a lesser extent due to the lower index match able to be obtained.

The effects that hydrocarbon contamination can have on concrete where investigated by Wilson et al [15]. Whilst the effects of petroleum hydrocarbons on pre-cast concrete should be negligible, both diesel and lubricating oil (15 w/40 grade car engine oil) had an approximate reduction in 28 day compressive strength of 15%. Furthermore not all contaminants affected the hydration process uniformly, for example both substances mentioned did not affect the strength gain at 7 days curing, whilst diesel only began to affected strength gain after 28 days. Such information provide an explanation for variations in compressive strength in some of the data gathered in this paper, especially if a combination of the two hydrocarbons are present in undeterminable quantities which could vary from sample to sample.

Figure 7A, B: Concrete degradation due to contamination

Visual evidence of foreign contaminants present during the curing process was recorded (figure 7). Although the chemical nature was unable to be determined, the samples most severely affected suffered noticeable reductions in compressive strength relative to lesser affected samples. This was not evident on any of the cement paste coated rubber aggregate samples. In addition to increased stiffness compatibility, the hardened cement paste coating may also act to a limited degree as a barrier preventing some of contaminants on the rubber from making ingress into the wet concrete mix, resulting in increased compressive strength.

5 CONCLUSIONS

- Cement paste coated coarse aggregates produced the most limited strength reductions out of the surface treatments used. This is attributed to the increased stiffness modulus of the rubber particles and the concrete matrix.
- Fine rubber limits strength reduction in concrete more so than coarse rubber between 10-15% respective aggregate replacement by volume.
- Coarse aggregate replacement by volume at 5% indicated a minor increase in compressive strength for both plain and cement paste coated rubber aggregates.

Relative to the data set, both uniform and variable reductions in compressive strength can occur when using rubberised concrete.

Uniform compressive strength reductions:

- The presence of rubber particles is detrimental to the compressive strength of concrete due to the low stiffness of the rubber causing it to act within the matrix similar to an air void, resulting in intensified crack propagation around the rubber particles.
- Rubber is responsible for increasing air content within the concrete both due to limitations with regards to aggregate grading as well as entrapping air in the surface morphology of the rubber aggregates.

Variable compressive strength reductions:

- The tendency for rubber particles to entrap air in their particle surface morphology can result in uneven distribution of rubber aggregate throughout the concrete matrix. The use of vibration apparatus also has limited effect on relieving this issue, especially at higher percentage replacement by volume of rubber aggregates due to their energy absorbing properties. The use of a tamping rod or extensive surface treatment such as cement paste coating are recommended to reduce this issue
- Intensified local crack propagation caused by the uneven distribution (or intra-sample non-homogeneity) of the rubber aggregates and therefore their weak interfacial transition zone bonds throughout the matrix can cause premature sample failure.
- Excessive quantities of cement paste with only minimal levels of natural fine aggregate to bond with may also form weak, mortar like areas of concrete as a result of being displaced by the crumb (fine) rubber. This may result in further strength reductions of the concrete matrix at both a general and localised level. The sizes of these formations are more prevalent at high rubber contents.
- Particulate residue imbedded on rubber particles can have an effect on the long term strength of rubberised concrete by interfering with the natural hydration and curing processes. However this is not necessarily an issue, depending on the level of refinement individual suppliers adhere to in their product manufacture.

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